

Eli Mirlis on the Future of Skilled Nursing

Skilled nursing facilities (SNFs) are changing and evolving to meet the needs of a growing aging population. With an increasing number of people over the age of 65, the demand for skilled professional is on the rise. The Department of Health and Human Services predicts that by 2050, half of all Americans will live in a community with 20% or more people over 65. This means that there will be an increased need for different types of nursing homes to provide care for this aging population. To keep up with this evolving industry, [Licensed Nursing Home Administrator](#) Eli Mirlis offers insight into what skilled nursing facilities will look like in the future.

The Future of Skilled Nursing Facilities

The most significant change that we are likely to see in the future of skilled nursing facilities is the aging population. As baby boomers age, they are more likely to need help with daily activities due to medical conditions like dementia or Alzheimer's. In addition, it's predicted that by 2050, half of all Americans will live in a community with 20% or more people over 65. This means that there will be an increased need for different types of nursing homes to provide care for this aging population, explains Eli Mirlis, [CEO at RegalCare Management Group](#). The National Association of Home Builders (NAHB) predicts that in 2030, one out of six new housing starts will be a care facility for seniors.

Skilled nursing facilities will also continue to evolve by offering additional services and amenities that appeal to the aging population on top of traditional healthcare needs. To meet these needs, facilities may offer assisted living and memory care as an additional service on site. Areas of focus may include environment and design features such as televisions, iPads and Wi-Fi connections which would allow residents to stay connected if they wish.

The industry will also continue to grow because it offers more job opportunities with salaries comparable to other industries. This is especially true when looking at jobs related to health care services where the median annual wage is \$48,860 per year according to Payscale.com

In conclusion, the future looks bright for skilled nursing facilities as they evolve alongside our changing society.

What will Skilled Nursing Facilities look like in the future?

The future of skilled nursing facilities will look very different from today. Today, SNFs use a semi-private model to care for residents in their homes. However, with an aging population, the demand for senior housing is increasing. This means that SNFs are shifting from caring for people at home to providing assisted living and senior housing at locations close to many communities--places where there is access to shopping malls and cultural centers.

To meet the increased demand for long-term care, SNFs will also need to offer short-term rehabilitation services. In addition to these changes, [Eli Mirlis](#) predicts that there will be an increase in service robots assisting with daily activity like cooking and cleaning rooms. There are also some interesting

developments in virtual reality as it pertains to health care as well as advanced diagnostic tools like CT scans and MRIs that can provide more accurate information about patient health without requiring them to go in person. These innovations will help with the transition into the future of healthcare.

How is skilled nursing evolving to meet the needs of an aging population?

It's been predicted that by 2050, half of all Americans will live in a community with 20% or more people over 65. So, how is skilled nursing evolving to meet the needs of this aging population? The first thing to understand is that the need for medical treatment is changing. Traditionally, patients would need a doctor visit and then a hospital stay. However, today it is common for patients to only need a doctor's visit and be discharged home without going to the hospital. This means that in-patient care facilities are seeing less demand.

The second thing to understand is that discharge from nursing homes have increased 30% in the last 5 years because of Medicare cuts. Medical costs are rising so these cuts are not sustainable and will eventually bankrupt skilled nursing facilities (SNFs). To combat this issue, SNFs have been focusing on other lucrative services like rehab, assisted living, and post-acute care. These new services generate revenue for SNFs and help them stay afloat during these uncertain times.>>END>>

Conclusion

Skilled nursing is evolving to meet the needs of an aging population. The future of skilled nursing facilities will address the need for skilled medical care, but also the need for a sense of community. It will be more than a place to visit when it's time to get medical care. It'll be a place to live, a place to visit and a place to find the support you need.